

SCIENTIFIC - THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S SPEECH

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Abstract. *In. An analysis of the researchers' scientific work is this article, the main concepts of the formation of children's speech, the stages of the formation of children's speech are classified presented.*

Keywords: *stages of speech formation, age periods, mimicry, linguistics, vocabulary, communicative, literary speech, grammar.*

It is known that the process of children's acquisition of their native language takes place in the same way in different children who are born and grow up in different environments. Researchers name and classify the stages of child speech formation in different ways. In particular, A.N. Leontev studies the formation of a child's speech in 4 stages:

Formation of speech:

- 1) the stage of language enrichment during preschool age
- 2) preparatory stage up to one year
- 3) the initial stage of language acquisition under the age of three
- 4) the stage of speech formation at school age

The famous linguist and psychologist G.L. Rosengrad-Punko considers it purposeful to study the formation of a child's speech in 2 stages:

- 1) Preparatory stage - covers the period up to 2 years.
- 2) Creating independent speech - the babysitter of the period after the age of 2.

In addition to these, A.G. Smolensiy divided the stage into 4 and M.M. Kolsova divided into 3 stages. Each of these stages greatly helps to thoroughly and perfectly study the stages of the formation of a child's speech.

In general, the formation of a child's speech can be divided into 4 periods:

1. The child's vocabulary is very shallow...
2. The number of words in the child's vocabulary increases very quickly.
3. Children's speech becomes more active by this time.
4. The level of language acquisition will be very high.

1. During this period, he only imitates external sounds, can pronounce monosyllabic words. Tries to express sounds through various gestures and actions (mimicry and gestures). During this period, the child tends to use words made up of repeated syllables.

2. Begins to pronounce syllables based on falling or alternating sounds. During this period, the child begins to control his own speech, observes the speech of the people around him, sometimes expresses a critical attitude towards them, and this situation gradually develops.

3. Vocabulary increases significantly. A child who initially uses words with 4-5 syllables can later pronounce words with more syllables. With the enrichment of the vocabulary content, speech thinking is also formed. The child begins to distinguish concreteness from abstraction. At the same time, it takes over the words of all word groups.

4. All complex aspects of grammar will be mastered. This process is unique to the conversation style. The ability to master literary language and written speech falls on children of school age.

Attention to ontolinguistics in Uzbek linguistics began in the 80s of the last century. Linguists O.Umarho'jayeva, M.Ismailov and M.Kurbonova researches in this regard are dedicated to some phonetic changes observed in the speech of Uzbek children and the psycholinguistic interpretation of children's speech. G. Iskandarova's practical observation and theoretical conclusions about the speech of preschool children can be considered one of the positive works carried out in the field of ontolinguistics in Uzbek linguistics.

As soon as a person is born, he feels the need for speech communication. From the first days of his life, the baby begins to perceive communication in the speech process through his senses. However, the child does not know how to use language norms, he does not yet fully understand the process of socialization, so he makes speech mistakes. Russian linguist T. G. Paymurzina says that ineffective communication is called communicative error and communicative failure in science. Communicative failure refers to the negative outcome of communication, failure of the speaker to achieve his goal, unplanned negative emotions and confrontational behavior. Therefore, a communicative error is a defective treatment or ambiguity.

Communicative barriers in the expression of thought, in the process of speech communication are clearly manifested mainly in the speech of preschool children. According to the results of a series of observations, the speech units used in the speech of preschool children are divided into the following types by linguist M. Qurbanova:

1. Forms of address consisting of one sound.
2. Address forms consisting of more than one sound.
3. Forms of reference that arise through the use of abstract lexemes representing the forms of reference that arise as a result of sound exchange.

1. A one-year-old and three-month-old boy addressed his brother for the first time through the sound "a". Although the child of this age has heard the lexeme "brother" several times in the process of communication, he preferred to use the method that has become a habit in his psychology. This speech expression, used in relation to a close relative, causes misunderstanding in those who meet the child for the first time and start communicating with him for the first time. The child did not have a purpose in using the monophonic form of address, he used the sound "a" because it was easy for him to pronounce. Later, even though the boy could pronounce the word "brother", he used to refer to his brother with the sound "a".

2. The two-year-old and one-month-old boy pronounced the word "blessing" in a pleading tone in his speech. In the process of communication, the child did not use any gestures or actions. This situation created difficulties for those around him, that is, those around him did not understand what the child wanted. They asked about "Bata" as an example of other words, for example, banana? The boy used "batta" again without shaking his head. So is it a fan for a child? when they asked him, he answered "hm" in the sense of yes. In the speech of a child of this age, such cases are observed in the pronunciation of words characteristic of the mastered layer. They have difficulty pronouncing consecutive consonants, resulting in a drop in sound.

3. In the speech of a four-year-old and three-month-old child, it can be observed that the word "disk" is pronounced in the style of "diks". A child of this age can pronounce one of the consecutive consonants in a word without omitting it. However, the difficulty in pronunciation

leads to a violation of the sequence in the child's speech. Children of this age should be asked not only to show what they want to say through gestures or actions, but also to explain it through speech.

4. The lexeme "biy naysa beyin" (give something) was used in the speech of a three-year-old and seven-month-old child. Often, adults want to tease or distract a child, and when they say "I'll give you something", they mean some kind of candy, for example, chocolate. As a result, if the child misses sweets, he will continue to appeal in the same way.

5. In the speech of a three-year-old and seven-month-old child expressed in the form of "I'm not working hard", there is a disproportion between form and content. In the dialect of the city of Tashkent, the phrase "my food is running out" means "my food is coming". The boy wanted to say that he did not want to eat. The defect in the child's speech is that he made a communicative error by using the inflectional affix "ma" twice, which prevented his speech from being understood.

Sometimes there are cases of using speech units by imitating sounds in children's speech. For example, the child gets used to pronouncing the sound coming from his father's car in the form of "" in his speech, or hearing the signal of the car and pronouncing it in the form of "dit-dit", "pap-pap". Later, even when he sees other cars, he keeps pronouncing the same sounds. He even starts pointing like that towards his father.

In conclusion, it can be said that in order to eliminate the misunderstandings in the speech situations presented in the above examples, to be more precise, to eliminate the communicative obstacles in the process of speech communication, it is necessary to review the syntactic devices and develop their simpler forms. It is necessary to use different methods of delivering the content of the speech to the child. Such an approach helps to eliminate the obstacles that arise in the communicative situation, helps the child to understand the mistakes in his speech, to develop the ability to formulate a sentence based on the unity of form and content. The solution to the problems mainly depends on the linguistic knowledge, skills and abilities of the people who communicate more with the child, and this situation requires a methodical approach from them.

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